

Jazz Harmony Analysis with ϵ -Transition and Cadential Shortcut

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ABSTRACT

Tonal Pitch Space (TPS) gives us a numerical distance between two chords, and enables us to give multiple interpretations of chord sequences as to their keys and degrees. Therefore, we can find the most plausible (*i.e.* sounds natural for humans) interpretation as the shortest path for the sequence. In this study, we first extend the TPS to include tetrads and natural/harmonic/melodic minor scales to cover those chords commonly used in jazz. Thereafter, we propose the notion of ϵ -transition, which is a free re-interpretation of a chord, to represent a pivot chord. Also, we propose the notion of cadential shortcut, which includes multiple chords to express a cadence, given as a shorter directed path in addition to the original sequences of possible interpretations. With this, we consider chord tri-grams as well as chord bi-grams. As a result, our method can reduce the number of the shortest paths, which results in an efficient algorithm to analyze jazz harmony.

1. INTRODUCTION

Harmony is one of the most fundamental components of music [15], and, like natural language, there must be some kind of syntax in harmonic sequences [1]. Harmonic syntax has been utilized in many music applications, *e.g.* audio chord transcription [3], melody harmonization [5], meter detection [8].

Tonal Pitch Space (TPS) [7] is a music model which provides a foundation to the harmonic analysis by defining the smoothness of chord connection as the numeric distance between two chords, given their keys and degrees. When a chord name is interpreted in multiple ways as to these keys and degrees, a chord sequence also gets multiple interpretations and results in a complicated network of connections. Among which, we can regard the path of connections with the shortest distance as the most natural interpretation.

Sakamoto *et al.* [14] have proposed a method to find the most plausible interpretations of chord progressions based on TPS. However, this method has some limitations: (1) tetrads (*e.g.* seventh chords) are not considered, (2) natural/harmonic/melodic minor scales are not distinguished,

(3) every chord has only one interpretation in an interpretation path, (4) direction is not considered, and (5) relations among more than two chords are not considered. Because these limitations tend to result in somewhat coarse analysis for jazz, the number of shortest paths often becomes enormous.

In this paper, first we incorporate tetrads and other minor scales to deal with the issues on (1) and (2). Thereafter, we propose two extensions on [14] to alleviate these limitations and conduct an experiment to confirm the effectiveness.

First, we introduce ϵ -transition, which is a notion in automata theory, that tolerates ‘free’ shift in states. In this paper, we regard a chord progression as a state change from a vertex to another in a directed graph. This ϵ -transition, however, allows us to reread a chord name to another without progression. This contributes the interpretation of pivot chord, and thus solves (3).

Second, we introduce the notion of *cadential shortcuts* to reduce the complexity and also to solve (4) and (5). If a certain sequence of chords matches a typical progression of cadences, we can skip the intermediate progressions and can jump to the cadences. This kind of shortcuts explicitly gives us the direction of chord progression to solve (4), and they enable us to consider tri-grams to solve (5).

This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we look back related works, In Section 3, we detail our new ideas. In the following Section 4, we show our experimental results and in the following Section 6, we evaluate cadence patterns. Finally, in Section 5, we summarize our contributions.

2. RELATED WORKS

There have been a lot of approaches to analyze musical harmony [6, 10, 12]. Our approach is based on one of those works to computationally analyze harmony syntax.

2.1 Tonal Pitch Space

TPS is a music model for the quantitative harmony analysis proposed by Fred Lerdahl [7]. It is proposed to complement Lerdahl’s other music theory the Generative Theory of Tonal Music (GTTM) [6], which applies the generative grammar to extend the Schenkerian theory. In this model, a chord is a pair of a key and a degree in it (*e.g.* interpretations of C major triad are as follows: I/C, III/a, V/F, IV/G, VI/e and VII/d) and distances are defined between these chord interpretations. The distance between

chord interpretations x and y can be calculated as eq.(1)

$$\delta(x, y) = \text{region}(x, y) + \text{chord}(x, y) + \text{basicspace}(x, y) \quad (1)$$

where $\text{region}(x, y)$ is a distance between keys and is defined as the length of the shortest arc on the circle of fifths. This distance cannot be calculated between major and minor keys; in such a case, one of them is converted to its minor/major relative key. For example, $\text{region}(C, d) = \text{region}(C, F) = 1$.

$\text{chord}(x, y)$ is a distance between degrees and is defined as the length of the shortest arc on the chord circle. When x and y are on different keys, degrees must be adjusted to either key.

Figure 1: basic space from I/C to iv/d.

$\text{basicspace}(x, y)$ is a distance on a structure called basic space which is composed of 4 layers (*i.e.* root, fifth, triad and diatonic) and each layer contains pitch classes reflecting the chord interpretation. Figure 1 shows the example when $x = I/C$ and $y = iv/d$, and the digits only in y are boxed. The distance on basic space is defined as the number of the boxed digits. In this case, $\text{basicspace}(I/C, iv/d) = 5$. The detail is explained in [7].

The calculation above is applicable only when x and y are in relative keys which are defined as follows:

$$\begin{cases} C(I) = \{i, ii, iii, IV, V, vi\} \\ C(i) = \{I, bIII, iv, v, bVI, bVII\} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $C(R)$ is the set of all relative keys of key R .

If x and y are not in relative keys, distance between x and y can be calculated as:

$$\delta(x, y) = \min(\delta(x, T_{R_1}) + \Delta(R_1, R_n) + \delta(T_{R_n}, y) \mid R_1 \in C(R_x), R_n \in C(R_y)) \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta(R_1, R_n) = \min\left(\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \delta(T_{R_i}, T_{R_{i+1}}) \mid R_{i+1} \in C(R_i)\right) \quad (4)$$

where T_R is key R 's tonic, R_z is chord interpretation z 's key. In other words, the transition from x to y must be considered as a combination of transitions within relative keys, and calculate the tonal distance for each combination, and then the shortest of these total distances is taken as the distance between x and y .

2.2 Former Approaches

Sakamoto *et al.* [14] have applied TPS to analyze chord sequences to find the most plausible interpretation as the shortest path based on the distances described above.

Figure 2: interpretation graph

Given a chord sequence, at first, their method extends each chord to its interpretations and constructs a graph whose edges have weights that correspond to the distances on TPS. Then it applies the Viterbi algorithm [16] to find the shortest interpretation paths from the start to the goal. Figure 2 shows an interpretation graph for chord sequence $C \rightarrow F \rightarrow G \rightarrow C$, and one of the shortest interpretation paths is $I/C \rightarrow IV/C \rightarrow V/C \rightarrow I/C$.

However, because this method is based on TPS, there are several limitations derived from this method. First, TPS basically is a theory for the harmony of period of common practice [11] and only consider major triads and minor triads and does not distinguish three minor scales, but it is insufficient to analyze jazz harmony which belongs to the period beyond common practice and for the most part composed of tetrads and is often characterized by scale-conscious performances. Also, TPS only defines the distances between two chord interpretations, so, for example, some chord sequences found very often in jazz like $II^1 \rightarrow V \rightarrow I$ cannot be dealt directly with it. Moreover, the distance becomes symmetric (*i.e.* $\delta(x, y) = \delta(y, x)$ for all x and y), but it seems not appropriate for harmony analysis; every chord progression should hold its own meaning, and the reverse order often does not make sense. Finally, the interpretation graph of [14] does not allow double interpretations on a chord in an interpretation path, therefore it cannot express key modulations by pivot chords, which is common in jazz. As a consequence, the original TPS cannot distinguish the subtle differences in the jazz chords, and the analysis results in a number of the shortest paths with the same value. To avoid such an ambiguity, we need to extend the TPS.

¹ We henceforth simplify the degree notation to use only upper case letters and omit accidentals, and disregard the difference of major/minor triads.

chord type	scale	deg	func
major triad	maj	I	T
	nat	III	T
	maj, mel	IV	SD
	maj, har, mel	V	D
dominant seventh	maj*	I	T
	maj*, nat*, har*, mel*	II	D
	mel	IV	SD
	maj, har, mel	V	D
	nat*, har*, mel*	VI	SDM
	nat*, har*, mel*	VII	SD
major seventh	maj	I	T
	nat*, har*, mel*	II	SDM
	nat	III	T
	maj	IV	SD
	nat, har	VI	SDM
minor triad	nat, har, mel	I	T
	nat, har	IV	SDM
minor seventh	nat	I	T
	maj, mel	II	SD
	maj	III	T
	nat, har	IV	SDM
	nat	V	D
	maj	VI	T
minor-major seventh	har, mel	I	T
diminished seventh	har	VII	D
half-diminished seventh	nat, har	II	SDM
	maj*	IV	T
	mal, mel	VII	D

'maj', 'nat', 'har', and 'mel' mean major, natural minor, harmonic minor, and melodic minor scales respectively. '*' is added if the chord is non-diatonic.

Table 1: Extended Chord Types

3. HARMONY ANALYSIS BY THE EXTENDED TPS

To redress the limitations described above, we propose the following three extensions.

3.1 Tetrads and Scales

First, we extend chord types and scales as in Table 1, which is obtained from [9]. This includes commonly used chord types, available scales, degrees, and functions. Some of them are non-diatonic chords and they are penalized according to the number of out-of-scale notes. The penalty cost used here is a parameter (we set this 1 for each out-of-scale notes²). Note that not all of the chord interpretations appeared in the original TPS are included in the table (e.g. second-degree triads of major keys).

² We chosen this value through our experiments, and the same goes for the other parameters in this paper.

3.2 ϵ -Transitions

Secondly, we introduce ϵ -transition to express paths which contain interpretation changes within a chord. For example, given a chord sequence $A7 \rightarrow Dm7 \rightarrow G7 \rightarrow CM7$, we may consider $A7 \rightarrow Dm7$ is in D (harmonic) minor, and $Dm7 \rightarrow G7 \rightarrow CM7$ is in C major, then $Dm7$ is a pivot chord, which bridges the key modulation and needs to be interpreted in both keys. We call this bridging edges ϵ -transitions. To bring this into the calculation, we modify the interpretation graph, as shown in Figure 3, duplicating every chord interpretation candidate so that each chord can have at most two interpretations at once without losing applicability of Viterbi algorithm. In Figure 3 all diagonal arrows within rectangles are ϵ -transitions, for example the white arrow inside the $Dm7$'s rectangle is the one described above. The cost of this interpretation change is a parameter (we set first this 0.5).

3.3 Cadential Shortcuts

Thirdly, to handle chord sequences of more than two chords, we extend the interpretation graph further to add new edges, which we call cadential shortcuts. Based on [9], we define the sequence patterns as certain sequences of chord functions and are listed in Table 2. These patterns are defined as sequences of chord functions within the same keys and their parallel keys, and the consecutive same functions can be wrapped into one. For example, pattern 5 ($SD \rightarrow D \rightarrow T$) can be applied to $Fm7 \rightarrow Dm7 \rightarrow G7 \rightarrow Cm7$. This method also enables us to take the direction into consideration and to assign different costs to reversed chord sequences. We search for all the patterns in Table 2 in the graph and for every identical pattern, we add cadential shortcuts connecting from the start node to the end node of the identical patterns and set the cost as that of the original path times 0.5 (this is also a parameter). In Figure 3 there found a pattern 5 ($SD \rightarrow D \rightarrow T$, shown by thick arrows) and added a cadential shortcut (shown by a dashed arrow). Our statistical analysis will be shown later in Section 4. This modification also retains the applicability of the Viterbi algorithm to find the shortest paths (for convenience of explanation, we expressed the cadential shortcuts as edges, but they are actually combinations of edges and nodes).

pattern	function sequence
1	$D \rightarrow T$
2	$SD \rightarrow T$
3	$SDM \rightarrow T$
4	$SD \rightarrow SDM \rightarrow T$
5	$SD \rightarrow D \rightarrow T$
6	$SDM \rightarrow D \rightarrow T$
7	$SD \rightarrow SDM \rightarrow D \rightarrow T$

Table 2: Cadence Patterns

Figure 3: extended interpretation graph

4. EXPERIMENTS

In this section, we examine the effectivity of these extensions by experiments.

4.1 Effectivity in terms of Disambiguation

We test if our approach can successfully disambiguate the interpretations by reducing the number of the shortest paths. We used JazzCorpus [4], which is an annotated corpus of tonal jazz chord sequences of 76 pieces totalling roughly 3,000 chords, and for each music piece we extract every successive nine³ chords in the sliding window and then apply the analysis described above and calculate the averages of generated graph complexity (node count and edge count) and the numbers of shortest paths. To compensate those chords which are not included in Table 1, we substitute them for similar chords (*e.g.* Csus4,7 with C7, C#5,7 with C7). The result is shown in Table 3 (a). It shows that while our extensions increase the complexity of the interpretation graphs the number of resulting shortest paths is reduced, especially when cadential shortcuts are applied.

This result is of arbitrary nine chords within pieces, so that there exist a lot of unnatural chord sequences to which hardly any cadence patterns can be applied. Then, we apply the same calculations, but this time the whole piece instead of nine chords sliding window, to several well-known jazz standards. The results are shown in Table 3 (b). Though each piece has different characteristics from the others, it can be seen that in all cases our proposed method can reduce the number of shortest paths.

Figure 4 shows a concrete example of the first eight measures of ‘Fly Me to the Moon’. White arrows represent ϵ -transitions and consecutive dashed arrows represent cadential shortcuts. As can be seen, the result of the original method contains many forks with the same costs, and in this example, there are $2^4 = 16$ paths. On the other hand, our method can find one shortest path. This is especially because the cadential shortcuts prefer those plausible cadences to the other equally costed forks.

³ We chosen this number in terms of processing time.

	#nodes	#edges	#shortest paths
original [14]	56	300	227.49
+ tetrads, 4 scales	55.01	287.22	172.76
+ ϵ -transitions	108.01	617.43	450.27
+ cadential shortcuts	131.58	657.06	74.18

(a) average

	#chords	original [14]	proposed approach
Fly Me to the Moon	34	8,495,104	384
Autumn Leaves	31	262,144	48
I Got Rhythm	53	over 1B	41,472
Giant Steps	24	193,536	3,888
Afro Blue	18	786,432	8
Blue Monk	13	3,072	2,560
I Remember Clifford	75	58,392,576	768

(b) shortest paths counts for each piece

Table 3: Graph Complexity and Shortest Paths Counts

4.2 Tree Representation

As can be seen from the example Figure 4(b), since our method manages to narrow down the candidate paths, the resulting paths usually contain a lot of cadence shortcuts which are connected with ϵ -transitions. This means that we can obtain the cadence chunks and their keys as a result of our analysis. We also can have the chord function chunks, which are identified by the key.

Music have some hierarchical structure, among which, the cadence and modulation between keys are fundamental basis of harmonic aspect. There are a lot of computational approach to obtain the harmonic structures [2, 6, 10, 13]. These studies mainly focus on the generative grammars based on the music theory of the chord function, the cadence and the key. In contrast to these approach, by utilizing the obtained cadence chunks and modulation informations from ϵ -transitions, we can generate a tree with a

Figure 4: analysis of ‘Fly Me to the Moon’. (a) original method [14] (b) proposed method

bottom up manner.

Specifically, the steps to generate a tree are as follows:

1. Generate a tree for each cadential shortcut.
 - The trees can be n -ary according to the length of cadential shortcuts, but we adopt (left-branching) binary tree after the convention of preceding studies.
 - However, every repetition of same functions is grouped under a parent node at first (n -arys are allowed here).
 - The caption of each leaf node is the corresponding function and key in the cadential shortcut, of each internal node is copied from its right most child node’s. We omit the scale information here for the sake of ease.
2. In case an ϵ -transition connects two cadential shortcuts, corresponding trees should be merged by one, where the root node of the previous tree as a child of the left most leaf node of the subsequent tree.
3. Generate a tree for each chord which is not assigned to any cadential shortcuts (the tree is therefore composed of only one node). Captions are blank.
4. Line up the trees generate above.

Figure 5 shows two examples of generated trees. Double lines represent ϵ -transitions, dashed lines represent cadential shortcuts, and dotted lines represent repetitions of same functions. In the case of Figure 5 (a), the left most tree (which represents the result shown in Figure 4 (b)) is composed of four cadences interconnected by three modulations. The second and third one have an identical structure with two cadences and one modulation. The last one consists of just one cadence. In the case of Figure 5 (b), all trees have just one cadence because no ϵ -transition is detected. Overall, our method seems to detect modulation sequences which finish in either relative keys.

Although the structures expressed by these trees are still very coarse, they seem to capture some basic structural

facts. So we believe our three extensions especially ϵ -transitions and cadential shortcuts can actually improve the expressiveness.

5. EVALUATING CADENCE PATTERNS

In this section, we utilize cadential shortcuts in an opposite manner to evaluate cadence patterns themselves. In the foregoing section, we adopted the cadence patterns in Table 2 as *de-facto* standards, but here we drop it and examine all bi-gram and tri-gram patterns. Moreover, we include patterns of degrees (*e.g.* $V \rightarrow I$). We use JazzCorpus and nine-chord sliding window again, but this time we replace the chord at the middle of each window with all possible chord candidates (*i.e.* 8 chord types times 12 keys), and predict the true chord by calculating the shortest path, this is possible because the chord where the shortest path passes should be the most natural and plausible chord. And also, we repeat this process for all bi-gram and tri-gram patterns, then evaluate each pattern by measuring the accuracy gain against the accuracy without any cadential shortcuts (18.8%). Accuracy here can be understood as the frequency the shortest paths select the true chord, therefore, the denominator is not affected by the lengths of cadence patterns. Intuitively, better patterns should be able to guide the shortest paths more strongly to the true chord, and vice versa.

The result is shown in Table 4. Common progressions like $II \rightarrow V \rightarrow I$ and their relative siblings (*e.g.* $IV \rightarrow VII \rightarrow III$) can be found in the best patterns. This result confirms the limitations of the former approach we mentioned above. Namely, the necessity of tri-gram was corroborated as is seen in Table 4. For example, the accuracy of $IV \rightarrow VII \rightarrow III$ is more gained than $IV \rightarrow VII$. Similarly, $II \rightarrow V \rightarrow I$ obtains more accuracy either than $II \rightarrow V$ or $V \rightarrow I$, and $SD \rightarrow D \rightarrow T$ does so than $SD \rightarrow D$ or $D \rightarrow T$. Also, the necessity of distinguishing the directions is corroborated by the fact that $D \rightarrow T$ is located in the best 11 while $T \rightarrow D$ in the worst 1. Note that Table 4 shows the accuracy gain, independent of the number of occurrence.

Figure 5: generated trees of the first eight chords of (a) the first half chorus from ‘Fly Me to the Moon’, and (b) the one chorus from ‘Autumn Leaves’

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we first extend the original Tonal Pitch Space to include tetrads and various minor scales, and thereafter, we have introduced ϵ -transition, that is a distance-free transition in two chords, and cadential shortcut, into the network of possible interpretations of chord progression. Inevitably, we have also considered the tri-grams and the explicit direction in them. As a result, we could reduce the number of the shortest paths and could obtain the efficient algorithm to find the most plausible interpretation, which results in a more reliable method to analyze jazz chord sequence.

There remain still several limitations for future research: (1) there is no distinction between long-term and short-term modulations, (2) values of the most parameters (*e.g.* coefficients for three elements in TPS, weight of ϵ -transitions and discount rate for cadential shortcuts) are not assessed theoretically, (3) chords are evaluated equally regardless of their lengths or relationships with beats, and (4) repetitions in chord sequences are not considered. To remedy these limitations, considering the relationship between more global structures would be necessary. Since our analysis gives local keys as well as the cadence types, we believe it would be an efficient step for extending the analysis to capture prolonged patterns by making an examination of relative importance of local keys or cadence types. And also, it might be better to employ more data-oriented approaches to find chord types and cadence patterns instead of just using predefined data tables (*i.e.* Table 1 and 2). Overcoming these challenges would lead to deeper under-

best patterns	acc(%)	worst patterns	acc(%)
IV → VII → III	55.85	T → D	-24.47
II → V → I	55.48	I → III	-23.35
II → V	49.41	III → V	-23.19
IV → VII	43.88	VI → I	-22.61
VII → III	28.83	II → IV	-22.29
SD → D → T	27.98	SD → D → SDM	-21.22
SD → D	27.39	D → SDM → T	-21.12
V → I	17.34	IV → VI	-21.06
SD → SDM	17.02	V → II → IV	-20.85
SDM → T	16.76	IV → I	-20.69
D → T	15.00	T → D → T	-20.69
III → IV	12.82	I → IV	-20.27
I → VI → II	11.17	VI → III	-20.21
VI → II → V	10.74	D → SDM → SD	-20.11
I → II	9.20	II → VI	-20.00

Table 4: 15 Best and Worst Patterns (**acc** represents accuracy gain)

standing of jazz harmony.

Acknowledgments

This work is supported by JSPS Kaken 16H01744.

7. REFERENCES

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